

NOTES

Complexes of Copper(II), Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II) with *N*-Benzoyl-*N'*-naphthylthiocarbamide

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METAL complexes with sulphur donar ligands are of special importance due to their versatile nature. In view of the importance, we report here the complexes of Cu^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} with *N*-benzoyl-*N'*-naphthylthiocarbamide (BNTC).

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. *N*-Benzoyl-*N'*-naphthylthiocarbamide was prepared by following the procedure reported by Horning¹. An alcoholic solution of the metal salts were added to solution of the ligand in acetone in 1 : 1 molar ratio. The resulting mixtures were stirred vigorously to precipitate the colour complexes which were filtered, washed with alcohol and acetone and dried under reduced pressure. Elemental analysis data are given in Table 1. The complexes were insoluble in water but sparingly soluble in some organic solvents.

Results and Discussions

The analytical and magnetic data are recorded in Table 1. As expected all the compounds are

found to be non-electrolytes and have very low molar conductance values, i.e. 2.5–3.3 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ for the Cu^{II} complexes, 3.5–4.5 for the Co^{II} complexes and 2.9–3.1 for the Ni^{II} complexes. The molecular weights determined by Rast's camphor method indicate that all the complexes are dimeric in nature. All the complexes except the complexes of Cu^{II} possess low magnetic moment values. The low values for the Co^{II} complexes (4.86–4.91 B.M.) may be due to spin-spin interaction and that for the Ni^{II} complexes (2.9–3.1 B.M.) due to diamagnetic impurity. The Cu^{II} complexes exhibit an electronic spectral band at ~15 400 cm⁻¹. The nature and position of the band are consistent with the earlier observations^{7,8} for pentacoordinated complexes. The complexes of Co^{II} show three bands at 19 415, 15 250 and 11 490 cm⁻¹ showing its resemblance with the known^{9,10} pentacoordinated species. The Ni^{II} complexes exhibit bands at 11 420, 12 500, 16 600, 17 500 and 21 275 cm⁻¹. These bands are in the same range are reported¹¹ for pentacoordinated Ni^{II} complexes.

All the metal complexes as well as in the ligand, show a broad ir band at 3 320–3 000 cm⁻¹ (NH). The CH stretching vibrations of aromatic ring which usually lies at 3 100–3 000 cm⁻¹ seems to have been overlapped with the NH stretching vibrations. The ligand as well as the metal complexes show four to five bands at 1 700–1 340 cm⁻¹, the first strong band appearing at 1 670 cm⁻¹. Considering the intensity and sharpness this band is assigned to C=O stretching vibrations². It undergoes a shift to a lower frequency region in all the metal complexes and appears near 1 600 cm⁻¹. It indicates that the oxygen atom is involved in the coordination. A strong band at 1 570 cm⁻¹ seems to arise due to ν_{C-N} of the ligand^{3,4}. The band is broad perhaps due to the mixing of naphthyl ring vibrations. But there is no significant change in ir spectra of the metal complexes which indicates clearly that the N atom is not involved in the coordination. The 1 215 cm⁻¹ (C=S) band appearing in the ligand at 1 215 cm⁻¹ shifts to a lower frequency region at 1 165 cm⁻¹ in all the metal complexes manifesting coordination of the sulphur atom. The 1 270, 1 240 and 1 151 cm⁻¹ bands in the ligand and also in the metal complex are attributed to the substituted aromatic ring⁵. The additional band at 1 500, 1 300, 1 020 and 930 cm⁻¹ to the nitrate complex are attributed to ν_{N-O} of the coordinated NO₃ group⁵. Perchlorate complex showed three significant bands at 1 260, 1 130 and 1 000 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to coordinated perchlorate group⁶.

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TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND MAGNETIC DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				μ _{eff} B.M.
		M	N	S	Cl/Br	
Cu ₂ (BNTC) ₂ Cl ₄	Pea	—	9.2	10.5		
	green		(9.7)	(11.0)		
	Light green	14.4	6.3	7.3	16.1	2.90
Cu ₂ (BNTC) ₂ Br ₄	Pale brown	11.8	5.3	6.3	30.3	2.10
		(12.4)	(5.7)	(6.5)	(30.5)	
Cu ₂ (BNTC) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₄	Grey	11.2	4.9	5.6	12.5	2.01
		(11.6)	(5.2)	(6.1)	(12.5)	
Cu ₂ (BNTC) ₂ (NO ₃) ₄	Black	12.8	11.3	6.5	—	2.04
		(13.1)	(11.6)	(6.8)		
Co ₂ (BNTC) ₂ Cl ₄	Violet	13.5	6.4	7.3	16.2	4.86
		(13.8)	(6.8)	(7.7)	(16.7)	
Co ₂ (BNTC) ₂ Br ₄	Green	11.2	5.3	6.3	30.5	4.91
		(11.6)	(5.5)	(6.3)	(30.9)	
Co ₂ (BNTC) ₂ (NO ₃) ₄	Red	11.9	11.5	6.5	—	4.87
		(12.3)	(11.9)	(6.8)		
Ni ₂ (BNTC) ₂ Cl ₄	Light green	13.5	6.4	7.3	16.3	2.90
		(13.9)	(6.7)	(7.6)	(16.7)	
Ni ₂ (BNTC) ₂ (NO ₃) ₄	Brick red	12.0	11.5	6.5	—	3.10
		(12.5)	(11.8)	(6.8)		

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**Copper(II), Nickel(II) and Cobalt(II)
Complexes of 2-(Phenylazo)-
2-cyanoethylethanoate**

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COUPLING of diazonium salts with β -ketonitriles have been studied extensively because the products have found use as yellow dyes and pigments¹⁻³. Transition metal complexes of these azo dyes are reported to have excellent fastness properties¹. However, there appears no systematic investigation on the structural aspects of these azo compounds and their metal complexes. The present communication reports the syntheses and characterisation of 2-(phenylazo)-2-cyanoethylethanoate (phenylazoethylcyanoacetate) and its copper(II), nickel(II) and cobalt(II) complexes.

Experimental

Phenylazoethylcyanoacetate was prepared as reported¹. For preparing metal complexes, an aqueous solution (10 ml) of the metal(II) acetate (1 mmol) was added to a stirred solution (50 ml) of the ligand (0.434 g, 2 mmol) in methanol. Sodium acetate was then added to maintain the pH of the mixture at 7-8. The solution was heated on a water-bath for ~1 h, concentrated to ~25 ml and cooled to room temperature. The resulting precipitated complex was filtered, washed successively with very dilute acetic acid (10 ml) and water, and recrystallised from hot ethanol.

Molar conductance of the complexes in ethanol (10^{-3} M) was measured on a Toshniwal conductivity bridge. Magnetic measurements were made on a Gouy balance and corrected for diamagnetic contribution. Uv-visible spectra were recorded on a Carl-Zeiss DMR 21 spectrophotometer, ir spectra ($4000-200$ cm^{-1}) on a Pye-Unicam SP 3-300

spectrometer and ¹H nmr spectra on a Varian EM 360L spectrometer. C, H, N and the metal content were done by standard methods.

Results and Discussion

All the metal complexes are non-conducting (sp. cond. $< 10 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$) and do not contain the anion of the metal salt used for their preparation. The analytical and physical data are given in Table 1.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL
DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	M p. °C	Colour	μ_{eff} B.M.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			
				C	H	N	Metal
[CuL ₂]	350	Green	1.92	53.25 (53.27)	4.20 (4.40)	16.50 (16.95)	12.80 (12.82)
[CoL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	355	Grey	5.12	53.52 (53.77)	3.92 (4.07)	16.80 (17.11)	11.91 (12.01)
[NiL ₂]	225	Red	—	53.25 (53.80)	3.92 (4.05)	16.85 (17.11)	11.43 (11.96)

Characterisation of ligand: Arylazo derivatives of β -ketonitriles can exhibit azo-hydrazone tautomerism¹. On the basis of uv, ir and ¹H nmr spectral data phenylazoethylcyanoacetate can be represented as **1a**. Thus, the uv spectra of the compound show a broad band (λ_{max} 355 nm) characteristic of the hydrazone tautomer⁴. The ir spectra show a strong band at 2 230 cm^{-1} assignable to the stretching of the cyano group⁵. Characteristic band of ester carbonyl at 1 700-1 800 cm^{-1} is absent. Instead, a strong band at 1 685 cm^{-1} and a medium intensity band at 1 615 cm^{-1} are revealed the former assigned to the stretching of hydrogen bonded ester carbonyl and the latter to C=N stretch of the hydrazone form⁵⁻⁷. In conformity with the intramolecularly hydrogen bonded structure, the spectra display a considerably broad band at 2 800-3 400 cm^{-1} . The absence of a methylene proton signal of the β -ketonitrile moiety and the presence of a low field one-proton signal at δ 12.95 in the ¹H nmr spectra clearly indicate that the compound exists in the hydrogen bonded hydrazone form^{8,9}. Signals due to CH₃, OCH₃ and phenyl groups are observed respectively at δ 1.25 (t), 4.30 (q) and 7.50 (m).

M = Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Co^{II}